

Organizational Effectiveness of Naval State University: Proposed Institutional Capacity Building

Jonas Abiertas Enriquez, DBA

Assistant Professor, College of Financial and Administrative Sciences, AMA International University, KINGDOM OF BAHRAIN

Corresponding Author: jaenriquez@amaiu.edu.bh

ABSTRACT

This research sought to study the organizational effectiveness of Naval State University (NSU), Biliran, Philippines. It was intended to answer the organizational effectiveness of the delivery of service by the present academic organizational set-up in terms of: Instruction, Research, and Community Extension. The study used the descriptive survey method through the aid of focus group discussion and researcher-made guided questions as the main instrument for data collection. There were items in the instrument that were patterned from the accreditation activities by the Accrediting Agency of Chartered Colleges and Universities in the Philippines (AACUP). The researcher tapped a third party who was an expert in conducting focus group discussions. The expert researcher who conducted the FGD was not connected with the Naval State University to avoid any biases. The activity of FGD was recorded with the consent of the key informants. The key informants were the key officials of the university. And they come up with only one answer in each item or indicator. The data were recorded according to the frequencies and corresponding percentage. After analyzing and interpreting the processed data, the Organizational Effectiveness of NSU in the areas of: Instruction, Research and Community Extension were rated as very effective. But some indicators were identified for needed improvements. And the institutional capacity building as designed in the study should be implemented accordingly.

Keywords-- NSU, HEI, Organizational Effectiveness

I. INTRODUCTION

Educational institutions have very many similarities to business entities. They are both created to accomplish specific organizational goals and objectives. For educational institutions, it focuses more on service, while profit motivates business organizations. It may differ in objectives but the processes and tools to achieve them are the same. A school's thrust is teaching students the theories and concepts about how things came about, while businesses utilize these theories and convert them to actual practices that will help the organization attain its goals and objectives.

Organizations usually start as small units; however, if they are properly managed, they grow. With growth, organizations undergo constant changes in their goals and objectives, structure, the people component,

services, and processes. These changes are necessary, if they are to grow and be competitive. One such educational institution is the Naval State University in the province of Biliran. Established as the Naval Institute of Technology but later it was converted into a state university by virtue of Republic Act 9718 in October 14, 2009. Since then, it has grown constantly, and to date it is the only state owned institution of higher learning in the province of Biliran, Philippines.

II. FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

This study was anchored on the organizational effectiveness of the three pillars of education namely; instruction, research and community extension. The study was attributed on the NSU's organizational effectiveness model for Higher Educational Institutions (HEI's) as emphasized by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) of the Philippines.

Organization was defined as "a deliberate arrangement of people to accomplish some specific purpose". "The organizing activity is a management function that involves the process of 1) determining what tasks are to be done, 2) who is to do them, 3) how the tasks are to be grouped, 4) who reports to whom; and, 5) where decisions are to be made" (Robbins, Coulter: 2002). This act known as organizing is carried out by managers as part of their planning function. Effectiveness on the other hand is the capability of producing expected output because of its essence of doing the right things. Effectiveness of a certain organization adds up to its ability to perform designated function within the boundary of input and output. The service rendered in the business shall be appraised to the quality of its productivity.

Bush (2011), emphasized that "effective leadership and management are essential if schools and college are to achieve the wide-ranging objectives sets for them by many stakeholders". As such, leadership is also essential factor in the model that contributes to the effectiveness of the business. According to the Office of the State personnel (2015), "leaders integrate values and expectations into the organization's leadership and management systems". According to Starratt (2011), "the work of teaching and learning courses to be seen as humanly fulfilling work for both the learners and teachers".

The ideas of Haag (2005), “if you set your school as an example, strategic management might include the chancellor, president, and various vice-presidents. Tactical management would include the deans. Operational management would include the department chairs and directors of academic programs. The final level would include instructors who are responsible for teaching your class. Strategic management provides an organization with overall direction and guidance. In the documents of Office of the State Personnel (2015), “an effective organization is structured so that it is able to do such things as: (a) respond quickly to an environment of rapid change, (b) efficiently meet its mission, (c) wisely use the knowledge, skills and abilities of its employees, (d) promote good communication and the flow of information necessary for every employee to do a good job, (e) encourage decision-making at the most appropriate level in the organization, and (f) link departments and work units so that they support each other”.

According to Nonaka and Takeuchi (1995), “the growing awareness of the complexity of organizations and with respect to organizational environments contributed to an emphasis on organizational differentiation and integration, information management, organizational learning, and most recently, is known as enterprise knowledge management”. Morgan (1997), emphasized that “there are numerous ways to conceptualize and model an organization, with profound consequences for criteria of effectiveness”. “In order for the organization to be effective it is essential that each part be in good working order. Each part must fit and work conjointly with other parts in order for the total organization to perform optimally. In an organization recognized for excellence those parts are aligned so that the whole is actually more effective than the sum of the parts” (Office of the State Personnel: 2015). Before any organizing is carried out, managers need to determine first how the organization will look like.

According to American Public Human Service Association ([APHSA], 2012, p.13), “In the organizational effectiveness (OE) approach, effective organizations are described operating systems that are made up of the following interconnected moving parts: the aim of the organization (strategy) shared and seen as important by staff within the organization and stakeholders external to the organization; resources put into the organization to achieve the strategy (inputs); ability the organization has to advance toward outcomes using available resources (performance capacity); activities of the organization towards outcomes (performance actions); results of system performance (outputs); changes in lives as a result of system performance (outcomes); and feedback from clients, staff, partners, key other stakeholders, and the community about how well the organization is achieving its desired outputs and outcomes (feedback from the environment). Feedback drives continuous improvement of strategy,

which in turn drives continuous improvement of inputs, performance capacity, and performance actions, which in turn drives continuous improvement of outputs and outcomes”.

According to Glickman et al. (2009), in recent years, education has been bombarded by packaged programs on “effective teaching,” “effective schools,” and “effective discipline.” And the CHED Memorandum Order (CMO) No. 46, series of 2012, defined quality as “alignment and consistency of outcomes that the institutional sustainability assessment for higher education is an instrument to determine how the learning institutions works for the standard set by the Commission on Higher Education”.

Srikanthan and Dalrymple (2002), said that “there is a considerable pressure on Higher education for a substantial improvement in its performance”. For Institutions of Higher Education in the Philippines, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) has released several CMO’s that served as guides for what it takes for a school to deliver quality education. For CHED there are three basic pillars for the holistic education of students: Instruction, Research, and Extension Services. Based on the information of Tomada et al. (2005), “most school transitions are characterized by sweeping changes in children’s social and learning environments”. Today’s undergraduate are pushing the academic library to rethink the ways in which it presents its most basic services. Implications for future directions in academic library services based on the new ways generation y learn and use the library are explored, (Gardner and Eng: 2003).

According to Perin (1998), “college faculty and administrators were highly concerned about student’s need for improved academic skills”. And the idea of Paulson (2002), “the unbundling the faculty instructional role is a useful concept for describing a variety of instructions. Likewise, Fair weather (1989) emphasized “the development of academic missions, including the importance placed by an academic institution on any set of goals at a specific point in time, has been influenced dramatically by changes in the national agenda. The simultaneous pursuit of instructional and research goals is essentially difficult in the modern research university”. In the idea of Paulson (2002), “translate research concerning direct and non-direct instruction into workable teaching patterns and clustering related teacher behaviors included in instructional: describing the teacher that center of attention who responds the pupils and organizes and present materials”.

Research in the university is embodied function. Thus instructors are mandated to perform such activity. According to Hair et al. (2007), “increasing literacy and the industrial revolution have change the way research is done”. CMO No. 23, Series of 2013 provides a major strategy for enhancing research productivity of HEIs in the Philippines, the institutionalization of a system of a rewards and incentives for outstanding research undertakings and outputs higher education

faculty/researchers. In the academe, faculty members are armed with knowledge. Learning should not end and it has no limitation. Exploration of new discoveries will add on the insights to the students. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2010), “it is a process of finding solutions to a problem after a thorough study and analyses of the situational factors.”

The CMO No. 08 Series of 2008, states that extension refers to the act of communicating, persuading and helping specific sectors or target clientele to enable them effectively improve production, community and/or institutions and quality of life”. The university should extend their technical resources to develop and promote well-being in the community.

The extension service as a major function of the learning institution is guided by the memorandum order of the CHED. The thrusts should be in lined with the expertise or specialization in relation to its vision and mission of the university. According to Andres (1998), “the aim of community development and organization is to help the people acquire a coherent meaning to life; it leads the people toward studying, perfecting, and achieving the system that is useful for the equilibrium and development of the human being because existence without direction/falsified in meaning generates moral decadence, socials, and personal and collective suffering”.

While the above mentioned studies may have some similarities with this paper but it is not a duplication of them in the sense that the time, respondents and environment are distinct and different.

III. OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the study were to determine the effectiveness of the Naval State University in terms of Instructions, Research and Community Extension and to propose institutional capacity building to improve the effectiveness of the university.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This study used descriptive survey method through the aid of focus group discussion and researcher-made guided questions as the main instrument for data collection. There were items in the instrument that were patterned from the accreditation activities by the Accrediting Agency of Chartered Colleges and Universities in the Philippines (AACUP).

The researcher tapped a third party who was an expert in conducting focus group discussions. The expert researcher who conducted the FGD was not connected with the Naval State University to avoid any biases. The FGD activity was recorded with the consent of the key informants.

The key informants of this study were evaluators and resource persons during the focus group discussion. They should come up with only one answer relative to the identified indicators and the actual implementations. They were key officials of NSU with administrative function and the same time with academic rank. Administrators under the Academic Group and with discipline on instruction, research and extension formed part of the respondents. They are the Vice President for Academic Affairs & External Affairs and the same time the Dean of Graduate School, Vice President for Planning, Research, Extension and Production Services, College Deans, Director of NSU Biliran Campus, Director of Research Services, and Director of Extension Services.

Researcher-made guided-questions served as the main tool for data collection. The guided-questions were focused on effectiveness of the delivery of service in academic set-up in terms of: instruction, research, and extension services which are quietly guided by the instrument of accreditation by AACUP.

The data gathered from the focus group discussion were tallied, tabulated and presented in tables. The data were recorded according to the frequencies and corresponding percentages.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1
Effectiveness of NSU based on Instruction

Item	Rating	Interpretation
Following the CHED policies and standards	4	Very Effective
Ensuring that faculty members possess the educational qualifications, professional experience, valid professional license (PRC passers) and teaching ability for the successful conduct of the school's programs.	4	Very Effective
Loading of Faculty (equitable distribution of loads)	4	Very Effective
Assigning of subjects to fit the educational and professional capabilities of instructors.	4	Very Effective
Aligning assignment of administrators to their field of specialization (i.e., Engineers to Engineering, Nurses to Nursing, etc.)	4	Very Effective

Clustering related courses to one specialized college / department (BSA, BSMA – Dept. of Accountancy; Marketing Mgt., HRD Mgt., Financial Mgt., Gen. Course – Dept. of Business and Mgt. etc.)	4	Very Effective
Assuring the equitable implementation of the Ranking and Evaluation System	4	Very Effective
Conducting regular evaluation of academic performance	3	Effective
Assuring the methods of instruction and learning process are evident	3	Effective
Seeing to it that the span of control that administrators have over their personnel is effective (i.e., the number of people that an administrator can supervise for them and their unit to be effective)	3	Effective
Preparing and implementing the Faculty Development Program (Career path, TNA)	4	Very Effective
Preparing, cascading, implementing, and reviewing the curriculum, syllabus, and offerings of the different programs.	4	Very Effective
Requiring faculty to have a consultation hours for the students	3	Effective
Providing adequate educational support structures, equipment and personnel (library, laboratory, College AVR)	4	Very Effective
Planning and responding to dynamic changes in the educational systems (OBE, ASEAN Integration, K-12 program)	4	Very Effective
Weighted Mean	3.73	Very Effective

In these items, the weighted mean or factor average is 3.73. The group cited the school's strict adherence to the requirements put in place by Commission on Higher Education (CHED).

CHED policies standards were discussed disseminated and become the model for the school's operation. All faculty members possessed the required educational qualifications, industry experience, and professional licenses in order to teach. NSU had adequate educational support structures (library, AVR), equipment (laboratory), and personnel overseeing them. The school had likewise started implementing and adopting the Outcome-Based Education (OBE) system into its syllabus. Planning sessions and strategic

meetings focused and the ASEAN Integration and the eventual implementation of the K-12 program have also been conducted and its implementation had started.

Items 8,9,10 and 13 were rated only effective and which was subject to the institutional development of the university. "In order for the organization to be effective it was essential that each part be in good working order. Each part must fit and work conjointly with other parts in order for the total organization to perform optimally. In an organization recognized for excellence those parts were aligned so that the whole was actually more effective than the sum of its parts" (Office of the State Personnel: 2015). Overall, this area, instruction is rated as very effective.

Table 2
Effectiveness of NSU based on Research

Item	Rating	Interpretation
Assuring an effective, efficient and functional Research Center for the University.	4	Very Effective
The Institution has a Research Manual which provides specific guidelines and procedures.	4	Very Effective
Ensuring that faculty members and students are trained and developed in the proper Research methods and practices.	3	Effective
Installing a system where all faculty members get the chance to attend trainings and seminars to enhance their research capabilities.	4	Very Effective
Developing and implementing the University Research Agenda.	4	Very Effective
Assuring the institution's research agenda is in consonance with institutional, regional and national priorities.	4	Very Effective

The research activities of the program are in consonance with the research agenda of the institution.	4	Very Effective
Conducting researches in line with the fields of specialization to improve operations, teaching content and procedures.	4	Very Effective
Completed and on-going research studies are periodically monitored and evaluated	4	Very Effective
Ensuring research results are published preferably in refereed journals.	4	Very Effective
Seeing to it that the research Center is staffed by fully competent personnel	4	Very Effective
Making sure that the Research Office is fully supported with their requirements (equipment such as internet, statistical software, and other resources and funding)	4	Very Effective
Allocating funds for faculty and student research activities.	4	Very Effective
Establishing linkages in the local, national and/or international levels to strengthen research programs.	4	Very Effective
Weighted Mean	3.93	Very Effective

NSU's Research Center was functioning very effective as shown in its programs and achievements with 3.93 weighted mean or factor average. The Research Manual provides the specific guidelines and procedures for all research activities. The University Research Agenda was constantly reviewed, updated, and cascaded.

The NSU Research Office was manned by fully competent personnel, from the Director down to the office staffs. It was provided with the latest computers, programs and software. A budget for operation and maintenance of the Research Center was always a top priority for the school board. The allocation funds for faculty and students research activities were based on the government's allocation.

The Research Center outputs and programs were done through linkages with other schools and other entities both local and international. There were already established linkages with several local schools, while that in the international level was on-going.

The only item that was rated as effective was item no. 3 and this was subject for the institutional development. Admittedly, the group agreed that some faculty members and students still lack adequate training in the proper research methods. There was a need to schedule and conduct more training sessions for teachers and students. This proposition was in lined with the idea of Perin (1998), in which "college faculty and administrators were highly concerned about student's need for improved academic skills".

Table 3
Effectiveness of NSU based on Extension Services

Item	Rating	Interpretation
Assuring an effective, efficient and functional Extension Service for the University.	4	Very Effective
The Institution has an Extension Manual which provides specific guidelines and procedures.	4	Very Effective
The institution's extension program is in consonance with institutional, regional and national priorities	4	Very Effective
Seeing to it that the Extension Services office is staffed by fully competent and dedicated personnel	4	Very Effective
Making sure that the Extension Services is fully supported with their requirements (equipment, promotion, and funding)	4	Very Effective
Responding quickly to, and supporting the various outreach programs	4	Very Effective

Faculty members conduct extension service in line with their fields of specialization.	4	Very Effective
Community participates in the formulation of extension activities identified as institutional thrust and priorities.	4	Very Effective
The need of expertise in a particular activity is initiated by the community.	4	Very Effective
Providing flexibility to the office in terms of policy and decision making.	3	Effective
The Institution provides opportunities for training to develop faculty competence	4	Very Effective
The institution encouraged students to participate in the implementation of extension services.	4	Very Effective
Weighted Mean	3.92	Very Effective

All the policies, guidelines and procedures for all activities of the office were found in the Extension Manual which basically the basis for the personnel involved. NSU's institutional, regional and national priorities serve as the guide for the various programs of the Community Extension Office.

To make it running as it should be, sufficient funds were set aside for the planning and implementation of identified projects. Aside from the financial assistance, the office was kept in the best level of effectiveness by its full complement of qualified and dedicated staffs that runs the unit.

For the programs to be responsive to the needs of the community, NSU's Extension Services Office took inputs from the various stakeholders of their target communities. These inputs were analyzed and discussed during the planning sessions with the community representatives.

Participants in the implementation of the community projects always include the students, faculty members and community leaders. Together with the support given by NSU's administration, this often results to sustainable and long term programs. It developed the sense of societal membership for the students and teachers' involvement.

In this area, only number 10 got an effective rating which was 3 and this was subject for institutional development. But the weighted mean or factor average was very effective with 3.92. It was highlighted during the discussions that the Extension office followed the final order from top management when it comes to policies and decision making. Their participation was only recommendatory.

After analyzing and interpreting the processed data, the following are the findings of the Organizational Effectiveness of NSU in the:

Area 1: Instruction was rated as very effective

Area 2: Research was rated very effective

Area 3: Community extension service was rated very effective

As provided in the CMO's of the authorized governing body for the educational standard, the Naval State University was compliant in delivering the three pillars of education namely; instruction, research and extension services. This was an affirmation of the mandates of CHED Memorandum Order (CMO) No. 46, series of 2012, "it defined quality as alignment and consistency of outcomes that the institutional sustainability assessment for higher education is an instrument to determine how the learning institutions works for the standard set by the Commission on Higher Education". Although the three (3) areas were rated very effective, there were certain items that were identified that needed improvements. And the designed institutional capability building in the study should be implemented accordingly.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it can therefore be concluded that while the general rating was very effective for the Instruction, Research and Community Extension, there were still minor details that rated lesser than very effective and which must be addressed and corrected in order to further improve the organizational effectiveness of NSU and bring it to the level of excellent.

There would be an implementation to the proposed Institutional Capacity Building for NSU as outlined in Chapter IV of this study. And there should be further studies in the following areas:

1. Effectiveness of the university in compliance with Institutional Sustainability Assessment (ISA) standards.
2. Effectiveness of the university in terms of typology as emphasized by Commission on Higher Education.

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